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Research Paper

Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patches of glibenclamide

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ABSTRACT

Glibenclamide, a hypoglycemic agent belonging to sulphonyl urea class. Sulphonyl urea causes hypoglycemia by stimulating insulin release from pancreas beta cells. Sulphonyl urea also may further increased insulin level by reducing hepatic clearance of the hormone. An attempt has been made to formulate transdermal patches using Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RS 100, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) as polymers, glycerol and propylene glycol as a plasticizers and Span 80 as a permeation enhancer by solvent casting method with aim of to study the release kinetics of drug with a view to reduce the dose frequency, improving patient compliance, greater therapeutic efficacy and to prevent its first pass metabolism to achieve a controlled drug release and overcome some draw backs such as gastric disturbance, hepato toxicity with improved bioavailability. The prepared transdermal patches were then evaluated for uniformity of thickness, weight variation, hardness, surface pH, tensile strength, swelling index (%), folding endurance, water vapor permeability, drug content. *In vitro* drug release studies of formulated patches were performed by studying the diffusion through human cadaver skin. The IR analysis of the sample was carried out for qualitative compound identification using KBr disc method. Out of eight formulations prepared, the formulation containing Eudragit RL 100 with propylene glycol as plasticizer showed complete and prolonged release with 98.02 % at the end of 24 hours. The data from the *In vitro* release was fitted to various kinetic models like zero order, first order, and Higuchi equations to determine the kinetics of drug release.

Keywords: Glibenclamide, transdermal patches, Eudragit RS100, Eudragit RL100, glycerol, Propylene glycol, *In vitro* release

INTRODUCTION

Today the pharmacist has entered in a new millennium with an objective of not only curing the disease but also to achieve the patient faith with providing least suffering to them. They are constantly busy in designing dosage form to fulfill above mentioned objective. Conventional administration of drug may some time prove to be in secure because of erratic response, over dosing and constant monitoring. Many fatal maladies require a dosage form that could release drug for a prolonged period of time at the predecided controlled delivery rate at a reasonable cost.

These observations have lead to generalization that for majority of therapeutic agents, a constant therapeutic level has to be maintaining with single dosing and showing least side effect with maximum patient compliancc. Thus the prime objective of controlled drug delivery system is to provide safe and efficacious constant drug leveling the body and preventing over dosing, with single dose of drug.

The objective of the study was to develop suitable transdermal drug delivery systems of glibenclamide and to study the release kinetics of drug with a view to reduce the dose frequency and to prevent its first pass

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metabolism, to achieve a controlled drug release and overcome some draw backs such as gastric disturbance, hepato toxicity with improved bioavailability.

Glibenclamide is an oral hypoglycemic agent widely used in the treatment of type II diabetes. Although it is rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Its duration of action

is short with relatively shorter half-life hence the dosing frequency is high¹.

The aim of the present study is to formulate and evaluate transdermal patches of glibenclamide as monolithic matrices using polymers in different combinations by solvent casting technique to achieve a controlled release of glibenclamide.

Table No. 1: Composition of formulations.

Formulation	Polymer (2 % w/v)	Plasticizer Glycerol (% w/w)*	Plasticizer Propylene glycol (% w/w)*	Permeation Enhancer Span 80 (% w/w)*	Casting Solvent	Drug (% w/v)*
F ₁	Eudragit RL 100	40	-	20	Methanol	1.06
F ₂	Eudragit RL 100 : PVP	40	-	20	Ethanol	1.06
F ₃	Eudragit RL 100	-	40	20	Methanol	1.06
F ₄	Eudragit RL 100 : PVP	-	40	20	Ethanol	1.06
F ₅	Eudragit RS 100	40	-	20	Methanol	1.06
F ₆	Eudragit RS 100 : PVP	40	-	20	Ethanol	1.06
F ₇	Eudragit RS 100	-	40	20	Methanol	1.06
F ₈	Eudragit RS 100 : PVP	-	40	20	Ethanol	1.06

* Based on Polymer weight

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Glibenclamide was obtained as gift sample from Zydus cadila healthcare Ltd, Ahmedabad. Eudragit RS 100, Eudragit RL 100 were obtained as gift samples from Intas pharmaceuticals Ltd., Ahmedabad and polyvinyl pyrrollidone was obtained from SD Fine chemicals, Mumbai.

Method for preparation of Transdermal patches

Transdermal patches containing glibenclamide (1.06 % w/v, i.e. 13.5 mg/cm²) were prepared by solvent casting technique-employing mercury as substrate². In the present study, total eight formulations were formulated using different polymers. Propylene glycol and glycerol were

incorporated at a concentration of 40 % w/w of polymer as plasticizers¹¹⁻¹⁴. And Span 80, at a concentration of 20 % w/w of polymer as penetration enhancer^{15, 16}. They are designated as F₁, F₂, F₃, F₄, F₅, F₆, F₇ and F₈ respectively. The detailed compositions of the patches are given in Table No.1.

Preparation of Casting Solution

The casting solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate polymers, plasticizer and penetration enhancer in suitable solvents (i.e. methanol and ethanol) using a magnetic stirrer to get uniform dispersion. The drug was added slowly to the solution and dissolved by continuous stirring for 30 minutes. The details of the solvents used for the preparation of casting solution are given in Table No. 1.

Casting of Matrices

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Table No. 2: Physico-chemical evaluation data of Transdermal patches

Formulation	Thickness * (mm) ± SD	Weight* (g) ± SD	Hardness* (g) ± SD	Surface pH*	Tensile strength* (kg/mm ²)	Swelling Index* (After 30 minutes)	Folding Endurance* (Mean ± SD)	% Drug Content
F ₁	0.153 ± 0.0015	0.062 ± 0.0015	219 ± 2.51	6.95	0.176	19.49	301.66 ± 5.01	97.65
F ₂	0.125 ± 0.0031	0.056 ± 0.0015	221 ± 7.50	6.95	0.179	19.75	311.66 ± 3.03	96.55
F ₃	0.149 ± 0.0015	0.051 ± 0.0025	235 ± 3.00	6.89	0.182	19.12	323.66 ± 4.04	98.45
F ₄	0.125 ± 0.0035	0.054 ± 0.0020	244 ± 3.60	6.97	0.181	20.36	289.66 ± 3.50	97.85
F ₅	0.162 ± 0.0011	0.063 ± 0.0020	218 ± 2.64	7.03	0.195	34.52	311.00 ± 7.55	95.65
F ₆	0.108 ± 0.0032	0.052 ± 0.0030	224 ± 5.29	7.11	0.195	37.16	271.00 ± 4.04	96.75
F ₇	0.163 ± 0.0015	0.061 ± 0.0020	257 ± 3.51	7.06	0.198	36.18	286.00 ± 4.50	98.05
F ₈	0.117 ± 0.0029	0.046 ± 0.0021	265 ± 2.08	7.15	0.194	36.52	313.00 ± 6.55	97.15

*Each reading is an average of three determinations

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Mercury was used as the substrate. Mercury is poured into the petridish. The mould was kept on the surface of mercury with smooth horizontal surface. About 10 ml of the solution was poured on the mercury surface (3.14 cm² area). The rate of evaporation was controlled by inverting a funnel over the

mould. After 24 hours, the dried patches thus obtained were cut into required size (2 cm diameter) by cork borer and wrapped in aluminum foil and stored over fused calcium chloride in a desiccator at room temperature for further use.

Table No 3: Kinetic data of Drug Release from F₁ to F₈

Formulation	Zero order equation		First order equation		Higuchi's equation	
	R ²	Rate constant (K) mg. h ⁻¹	R ²	Rate constant (K) mg. h ⁻¹	R ²	Rate constant (K) mg. h ⁻¹
F1	0.9978	3.5400	0.7742	0.1289	0.9704	21.929
F2	0.9990	3.1569	0.7888	0.1271	0.9657	19.538
F3	0.9982	4.1612	0.7586	0.1317	0.9704	25.777
F4	0.9905	3.5778	0.7732	0.1291	0.9704	22.162
F5	0.9888	2.9490	0.7914	0.1257	0.9704	18.267
F6	0.9939	3.3437	0.7795	0.1280	0.9704	20.713
F7	0.9956	3.8265	0.7665	0.1303	0.9705	23.703
F8	0.9951	3.4071	0.7754	0.1285	0.9709	21.109

Evaluation of the prepared formulations

Uniformity of thickness³

The thickness of the patches was measured at five different sites on three patches from each batch using micrometer (Chaun japan) and the average was calculated.

Weight variation⁴

Weight variation test was done by weighing three patches individually from each batch. The average weight of the patch was taken as original weight.

Hardness⁵

Performing the test on different three patches individually from each batch by fabricated hardness instrument and the average was calculated.

Surface pH⁶

Surface pH of the patch was determined by allowing them to swell in closed petridish at room temperature for 30 minutes in 0.1 ml of double distilled water. The swollen devices were removed and placed under digital pH meter to determine the surface pH.

Tensile Strength⁷

The tensile strength of the transdermal patches was measured using tensile strength instrument (locally fabricated instrument). Average reading of three patches from each batch was taken as the tensile strength.

Swelling index⁶

Swelling index was determined by immersing the patch in a preweighed stainless

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steel basket in 20 ml of freshly boiled and cooled phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at 37^o C. The weight of the swelled patch was determined at specified time intervals (every 5 minutes). The procedure was continued till there was no increase in the weight. And the relative weight gain (water uptake) was calculated using the following relationship.

$$\text{Swelling Index} = (W_t - W_o/W_o) \times 100$$

Where W_t = weight of patch at time t

W_o = weight of patch at time zero.

Folding Endurance⁸

The folding endurance was reassured manually for the prepared patches. It is expressed as number of time the patches are folded at the same place either to break the patch or to develop visible cracks. This is important to check the ability of sample to withstand folding. This also gives an indication of brittleness. The number of times the films could be folded at the same place without breaking gives the value of folding endurance.

Drug content

The uniformity of drug content of the transdermal patches was determined, based on the weight of drug and polymers used by means of a UV spectrophotometric method. Formulations F₁, F₃, F₅, and F₇ were dissolved separately in 10 ml of methanol and F₂, F₄, F₆, and F₈ were in 10 ml of ethanol and stirred for 30 minutes. The resulting solutions were quantitatively transferred to volumetric flasks, and appropriate dilutions were made with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The resulting solutions were filtered and analyzed for Glibenclamide content at 236 nm in UV spectrophotometer. The average reading of three patches was taken as the content of drug in one patch.

In vitro Permeation studies Permeation cell:

A modified Keshary-chien cell was used for *in vitro* permeation study of transdermal patches. The diffusion cell was fabricated from borosilicate glass and consisted of two compartments receptor and donor. The cell had an effective receptor volume of 75 ml and having inner diameter of 2.5 cm and a side arm for easy withdrawal of samples.

Preparation of Human Cadaver Skin:

The human cadaver skin obtained from cadaver brought for autopsy at Sheth V. S. General Hospital, Ahmedabad was utilized for the study. After taking consent of relatives, the skin from the chest region of the cadaver was taken in sealed evacuated plastic bag containing ice. The sample was stored in the evacuated plastic bag in the deep freezer at 20^o C until use. The skin from poisoning, hyperthermia and burnt cases were not taken for study. Before use, the skin was allowed to thaw at room temperature, following which all subcutaneous fat was removed with the scalpel. The hairs were removed with the help of pair of scissors.¹⁷ Epidermal layers were separated from the remaining skin by immersing each skin section in water at 60^o C for 2 minutes. The epidermis was teased from the dermis using forceps; the separated epidermal layer was used as such for the skin permeation studies. At the time of use, the epidermis was spread on the cell and allowed to equilibrate with receptor fluid for 15 minutes before commencing the experiment.¹⁸⁻¹⁹

Procedure:

A modified Keshary-chien cell was used for evaluating drug permeation profiles across human cadaver skin. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was used as a receptor medium, was filled in the diffusion cell. It was placed on a magnetic stirrer with a Teflon bead placed inside for uniform distribution. The contents of donor and receptor compartments were

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separated by placing freshly human cadaver skin in between two compartments. The human cadaver skin was mounted in such a way that the upper side of the skin was continuously remained in intimate contact with the transdermal patch in the donor compartment. Transdermal patch of 2 cm diameter was overlaid on the skin preparation with good contact and placed in between two halves of the diffusion cell. The top side was covered with aluminum foil as backing membrane. The receptor fluid was agitated using magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained at $37^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ} \text{C}$. The amount of drug permeated into the receptor solution was determined by removing 1 ml of sample at hourly intervals for 24 hours. The withdrawn volume was replaced with an equal volume of fresh buffer solution. The absorbance was read at 236 nm. There was no interfering of soluble skin proteins in the UV absorbance because of pretreatment of the skin sample before using in the permeation studies.

Skin irritation test¹⁰

The primary skin irritation test was performed on seven healthy albino rabbits, weighing between 2.0 to 3.5 kg. Drug free patches of 4 cm² area were prepared and were used as test patches, while adhesive tape (USP) was used as control. The test was conducted on unbraided skin of the rabbits. The control and test patches were placed on the left and right dorsal surfaces of the rabbit respectively. The patches were removed after 24 h with the help of alcohol swab and the skin was examined for erythema and edema.

Drug excipients compatibility studies

The drug- excipients studies were confirmed by infrared spectrophotometer using KBr disc method. The IR spectra obtained was elucidated for important groups. The identification peaks were found i.e. -C = O stretching (1713.9 cm^{-1}), peaks at 680.8 cm^{-1} and 904.9 cm^{-1} indicates aromatic compound, -CH stretching of CH_3 (2856.5 cm^{-1} and

2935.8 cm^{-1}) and -NH stretching (3327.8 cm^{-1}). The IR spectrum is depicted in figure 3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Efforts were made to prepare the transdermal patches of glibenclamide using polymers such as Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RS 100 and polyvinyl pyrrolidone. The physico-chemical evaluation data presented in Table No. 2 indicates that the thicknesses of the formulations varied between 0.108 ± 0.0032 to 0.163 ± 0.0015 mm. The result showed that the thickness was uniform. The weight of the patches varied between 0.046 ± 0.0021 to 0.063 ± 0.002 gm. The hardness of the patches was found vary with the nature of the polymer. It was found to vary between 219 ± 2.5166 to 265 ± 2.0816 . The drug content of the formulations was determined according to procedure described in methods. The drug content in all formulations was found to contain 95.65 % to 98.45 % of glibenclamide. The release of drug from the best batch of transdermal patches i.e. F₃ is 12.96 mg/cm^2 of patch at 24 h and it is able to deliver the expected amount of drug required for treatment of diabetes. So the patch of 2 cm diameter would be adequate to meet the required drug release per hour. The release profile of the formulations is shown in the figure 1 to 2. The targeted release profile expected from the formulation was more than 90 % of the drug should be released at 24 h and should follow the zero order release kinetics. And it was observed by fitting the drug release data to different release kinetic models. The results obtained by fitting the drug release data to different models are shown in Table No. 3. Results indicated that the order of permeation of the drug from different monolithic polymeric membranes was Eudragit RL 100(Propylene glycol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RS 100(Propylene glycol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RL 100: PVP (Propylene glycol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RL 100(glycerol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RS

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Figure 1: In vitro release of glibenclamide from F1, F2, F3 and F4 formulations

Figure 2: In vitro release of glibenclamide from F5, F6, F7 and F8 formulations

Figure 3: IR Spectra of Drug and Drug loaded formulation

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100: PVP (Propylene glycol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RS 100: PVP (glycerol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RL 100: PVP (glycerol as plasticizer) > Eudragit RS 100 (glycerol as plasticizer). The *in vitro* release data was also subjected to model fitting analysis to know the mechanism of drug release from the formulations by treating the data according to zero order, first order and Higuchi equation. The results are shown in Table No. 3. It indicates that the release of drug from the patches might have followed zero order kinetics. Also, lower variation was obtained for zero order release rate constant as compared with first order release rate constants indicating a zero order release pattern from the formulations. The permeability was increased with stripping of the skin to remove the stratum corneum that act as a barrier of skin permeation. The results of skin irritation test showed negligible erythema with prepared patches when compared to control. The absence of edema indicated that these polymeric patches were compatible with the skin and hence can be used for transdermal application.

CONCLUSION

A good Transdermal patch containing Glibenclamide can be formulated by solvent casting technique using Eudragit RL 100 as film former and propylene glycol as plasticizer. Such monolithic Transdermal patches are advantageous in providing effective treatment for diabetes with enhanced patient compliance.

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